

**Centre of Excellence in Simulation of Weather and Climate in Europe
Phase 3**

**Service assessment 1
Milestone M4.3**

ESiWACE3 Milestone M4.3

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Introduction

As the demand for higher resolution and more accurate weather and climate simulations increases, the need for exascale supercomputers becomes more pressing. Modern (exascale) supercomputers increasingly rely on graphics processing units (GPUs) as the major source of compute power. However, the process of porting existing weather and climate modelling codes to these new systems presents several challenges.

As many existing weather and climate modelling codes are designed to run on traditional CPU-based supercomputers, significant efforts are required to port the codes to new supercomputers and efficiently utilize GPUs. The transition can be difficult for researchers and developers who are accustomed to working with traditional CPU-based systems and may not have experience with programming and optimizing GPU code.

ESiWACE3 Services create collaborative projects that couple developers of weather and climate models with Research Software Engineers (RSEs) who have experience with both HPC and the weather and climate domain. These collaborations last for about a whole year during which the model developers and the research software engineers regularly work together to give guidance and assistance on optimizing and porting weather and climate models to modern HPC systems. This requires a deep understanding of both the weather and climate domain and high performance computing, which is the unique expertise provided by ESiWACE3 engineers. The ESiWACE3 engineers, in close collaboration with the model developers, make substantial modifications to the model source code that advance the model's capability to use modern HPC systems. A crucial factor in ESiWACE3 service projects is that the service project is only granted if the applicant can guarantee that the project will impact the upstream version of the software. This is the version of the code that will be used by countless end users on all kinds of HPC systems across Europe and beyond.

The ESiWACE3 project creates two services. Service 1: "Collaborations to prepare Europe's Weather and Climate Models for pre-exascale systems" focuses on porting and refactoring weather and climate models to new computing architectures, such as GPUs. Service 2: "State-of-the-art development tools for Weather and Climate" focuses on helping weather and climate model developers to adopt the tools developed by ESiWACE3 Work Package 1-3.

Call process

The Service 1 and Service 2 calls for proposals are published on the ESiWACE3 website. The call for proposals document¹ gives a detailed description of the purpose of the calls, what can be applied for, who can apply, how to prepare an application, and specific conditions that apply to the calls.

The assessment procedure is also explained in detail in the call for proposals document. The proposals are reviewed in two phases. First, a technical feasibility and software sustainability check is performed. This technical review decides which proposals make it to round 2, the scientific review. A scientific review committee is established for each round of proposals to be evaluated, comprising established researchers in the weather and climate community, both internal and external to the ESiWACE consortium, who take the final granting decision based on scientific relevance, importance to the community, and potential scientific impact of the work.

¹ <https://www.esiwace.eu/services/software-support/esiwace3-2024-service1-cfp.pdf>

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This report was written in June 2024, Month 18 (M18) of the ESiWACE3 project. So far, we have held 3 calls for Service proposals. The table below shows the total number of applications per call and the names of the projects that have been accepted in this call.

Date of Service 1 call closing	Submitted proposals	Accepted proposals
28-06-2023	4 in total	DALES, GLOBO, ESMValTool
01-11-2023	6 in total	OGSTM-BFM, CAMP, MESSy, EC-EARTH4 (to start in July 2024)
03-06-2024	5 in total	review is in progress

Service 2 was scheduled to start one year after the start of Service 1, so in Month 18 of the project. As such, only one call for Service 2 projects has been organized so far. The Service 2 call was requesting proposals on the use of the AutoRPE, Spack, and Kernel Tuner tools. Two proposals have been received for the Service 2 call, one on Spack and one on Kernel Tuner. The proposal on the use of Spack has been rejected, because it did not fit the scope of the call. The proposal on using Kernel Tuner to optimize models with mixed-precision techniques on GPUs has been accepted and the project is scheduled to start in September 2024.

The following section presents a status update of the work performed so far in the running Service 1 projects. Do note that these are not final results and several projects have only recently started.

Service 1 projects

This section gives an overview of the progress made so far by the currently granted Service 1 projects. Note that the projects are still running and work in some projects has only just started. The EC-EARTH4 Service 1 project is not included, because work in that project will start in July 2024 (one month after this report was written).

DALES

The Dutch Atmospheric Large Eddy Simulation DALES is a Fortran90 program designed to model atmospheric processes at high resolution, such as clouds, convection, precipitation and turbulence. DALES includes the optional transport and reactions of chemical compounds and is linked to the external RRTMG radiation library.

The aim of this service project is to port DALES to GPUs using OpenACC. Recently, this effort has been initiated by the DALES developers for non-precipitating cases excluding radiation. The goal of this service is to extend the GPU implementation to include more realistic situations, by (a) porting microphysics schemes to GPUs and (b) performing the radiation computation on the GPU.

Figure 1: Baseline situation before work was started. Single-GPU weak scaling of the DALES bomex dry physics test case, comparing a regular compute node (EPYC 7H12) to a single NVidia A100 chip. Test was performed on the Dutch national supercomputer Snellius.

In this period, we have started to interface DALES with the radiation software RTE-RRTMGP (<https://github.com/earth-system-radiation/rte-rrtmgp>), which exploits fine-grained parallelisation of radiation calculations and features multi-GPU calculations through OpenACC. This will allow a simple speed up of radiation calculations in DALES as shown in Figure 1. For now simple features are ported, as longwave, molecular radiation. We will next focus on porting cloud radiation and extending over the whole spectrum. Furthermore, we have ported the simple bulk microphysics scheme to GPUs using OpenACC and implemented the DALES restarting functionality for GPU-resident runs.

GLOBO

GLOBO is a general atmospheric circulation numerical model developed at the Institute of Atmospheric Sciences and Climate (ISAC) (CNR, Italy). GLOBO is currently used as a research tool predictability study on different time scales ranging from the medium range to the subseasonal scale. It is also used as an operational forecasting tool with an Euro-Mediterranean focused 7-day forecast and a 32-day ensemble forecast, which is issued once a week².

The specific objective of this collaboration is to improve the exploration of multi core HPC resources and study the identified specific bottlenecks related to parallelization of I/O operations or any other optimization that would pave the way for a future GPU-acceleration of the GLOBO model.

The code was ported to Atos' internal cluster and the build system adapted for several compilers including an ifort toolchain. This showed a difference in performance of about 25% in favour of ifort compared to the gfortran toolchain that is usually used. Profiling indicates this comes mostly from better vectorization. A major part of the execution resides inside MPI communications with a significant imbalance between the master processor and others.

² <https://www.isac.cnr.it/dinamica/projects/forecasts/>

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The scripted build system of GLOBO has been replaced by a recent and modern approach based on CMake. This leads to a 5 to 90 times faster compilation without any sequential phase or erroneous file dependencies. A first optimization has also been applied by inlining a function leading to a 15% improvement thanks to a better vectorization from the compiler.

The next steps will be to study the IO efficiency and to work on the imbalance between the master processor and others.

ESMValTool

The Earth System Model Evaluation Tool³ (Eyring et al., 2020) is a community-developed, open-source software tool for the evaluation and analysis of output from ESMs. For example, it allows comparing output of single or multiple models against results from previous versions or against re-analyses and observations. ESMValTool provides diagnostics for several different realms (e.g., atmosphere, ocean, land, etc.), and is developed with contributions of over 200 developers from more than 60 international institutions.

The goal of this project is to optimise the code path of standard workflows in ESMValTool and improve the data loading speed of ESMValTool on various high-end supercomputers, such as the Levante system at DKRZ. A secondary goal is to allow object-stored climate data as input for the tool, to make a connection to the Pangeo community.

ESMValCore, the framework running ESMValTool workflows, comes with approximately 60 'preprocessor' functions. These are functions that perform common tasks, such as regridding and computing statistics, that are used by many of the workflows. An important step in achieving good computational performance is to make sure these functions use Dask arrays instead of plain Numpy arrays. This results in lower minimum memory requirements and improved parallelism. 52 preprocessor functions are already using Dask arrays and work is in progress on another 7.

We have profiled two distinct use cases ('recipes') of the ESMValTool, representing both coarse-scale IPCC-ready analyses on climatological time scales and shorter seasonal processing jobs for high-resolution climate data, as shown in Figure 2. We have identified several potential bottlenecks, often stemming from redundant loading of data from disk. We have removed some of these bottlenecks in the metadata processing within the Iris library, resulting in a ~50 percent speedup of the former scenario. Another conclusion from profiling the use cases is that runtime could benefit from improved parallelism of the metadata computations (i.e. computations on spatial and temporal coordinates as opposed to the main variable of interest). A prototype that implements improved parallelism for metadata computations has been developed.

³ <https://doi.org/10.5194/gmd-13-3383-2020>

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Figure 2: flame graph of the IPCC-ready analysis script, with the removed redundant metadata calculation sections highlighted in red. Test performed at DKRZ Levante system, with data on the Lustre scratch file system.

A new episode has been added to the online ESMValTool course to train the ESMValTool community in configuring Dask, as shown in Figure 3. in order to work efficiently on the HPC systems to which they have access. It is currently under review by the community.

Figure 3: The new episode in the ESMValTool course on configuring Dask for use with the ESMValTool.

OGSTM-BFM

OGSTM-BFM is a transport reaction model applied to marine biogeochemistry used both for process study on the marine ecosystem, short term forecast and climate projection, developed by the BFM consortium⁴.

The main objective of the project is to port on GPU the different routines of OGSTM and BFM. The developers have identified several important routines, the complex carbonate equations solving routine from BFM, and the horizontal and vertical diffusion routines from OGSTM. All these objectives have been met, leaving more time for GPU porting and optimisations. We are confident we will be able to fully port OGSTM-BFM on GPU by the end of the project and do a basic optimisation pass on the code. With reference to Figure 4, for now we have reached a speedup of about 5 compared to the old GPU version (see the next figure) but data transfers are still a major bottleneck. By porting more code on GPU we will be able to only transfer data back to CPU when

⁴ <https://bfm-community.github.io/www.bfm-community.eu/#documentation>

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dumping output to disk. We still expect MPI communications to be a significant bottleneck and we don't know whether we will be able to optimise this aspect within the project timeframe.

Figure 4: Nsight Systems trace showing original GPU port status (at the top) compared to the current GPU port status (on the bottom). We can already see a speedup factor of 5, time being dominated by data transfers (shown in green and purple at the top).

The next high priority step is to support the developers with deploying OGSTM-BFM on the Leonardo supercomputer as they are facing I/O issues.

CAMP

The Chemistry Across Multiple Phases (CAMP) is a software for a flexible treatment for gas- and aerosol-phase chemical processes for incorporation in models of diverse scale, from box models up to global Earth System models. Key features of this novel framework are: (i) an abstracted aerosol representation that allows the same chemical mechanism to be solved on models with different aerosol representations (e.g., binned, modal, or particle-resolved), (ii) a run-time model configuration through a combination of JSON input files, and (iii) a flexible implementation in

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heterogeneous CPU/GPU architectures. CAMP has been deployed in the particle-resolved PartMC model and in the Multiscale Online Atmosphere Chemistry (MONARCH) chemical weather prediction system for use at regional and global scales.

Before deploying Marenostrum 5, we set a reference experiment of the CAMP GPU in the MONARCH model. Table 1 summarises the results:

Test	Accuracy error [%]	Speedup
Box	0.02	8x
MONARCH	0.42	7x

Table 1. Speedup and accuracy error using 4 GPUs against 40 CPU cores, using a full node and a one-day simulation. "Box" corresponds to a box model that simulates MONARCH input, which eases development from running MONARCH. The accuracy error is calculated as the Normalised Root Mean Square Error over the range, averaged over the cells, and obtained from the last time step.

We also deployed CAMP on Marenostrum 5. Now, we are developing a heterogeneous CPU+GPU version. In this version, we port the rest of the solver procedure to GPU, reducing significantly the data transfers. The accuracy error remains equal to the previous version, and we are now profiling this version.

In future work, we expect to deploy CAMP+MONARCH on Marenostrum 5 and provide profiling metrics and performance analysis of the box model CAMP and MONARCH, including different configurations of load balancing between CPU and GPU.

MESSy

The Modular Earth Submodel System (MESSy)⁵ is a software project providing an infrastructure for coupling atmospheric models (e.g., ICON, ECHAM, COSMO) and specialised ESM components, the so-called submodels (e.g., physical parameterizations, chemistry packages, diagnostics) via generalised interfaces for standardised control and coupling. MESSy will be ported to GPU submodel wise. As MESSy contains some computationally expensive process implementations, speedup on the process level can be taken as granted. However, if only individual processes are ported, frequent copies of high amounts of data between host and device will diminish the gain in speed substantially. In order to accelerate the model as soon and as much as possible, i.e. already during the porting process, the data transfer between host and device needs to be optimised, so that the speedup of individual code sections can be decoupled from the memory update.

Due to unexpected bottlenecks in staffing, the work could only be started initially. Collaboration with the MESSy developers has been adapted accordingly and we expect to be able to resume full service support in July 2024.

⁵ <https://messy-interface.org/>

Evaluation

This section assesses how the ESiWACE3 services are running overall. There have been several challenges that we have encountered in Service 1, in particular with regard to staffing. The CAMP and MESSy projects have both been delayed due to staffing issues at BSC and DKRZ, respectively. Fortunately, these positions have now been filled and the service projects are up and running again.

In terms of the reach of the services, we still see that the service applications are mostly received from the direct network of ESiWACE3 partners, in particular from the Netherlands, France, Germany, and Spain, which means that our communication towards the wider European community can and should be improved further.

Due to Service 2 being highly specialized towards certain tools, it is expected that the number of applications is lower than for Service 1. Nonetheless, we have identified some improvements with regard to how Service 2 is advertised. For example, on the website there is visually very little distinction between Service 1 and Service 2, while the two services serve different purposes and possibly even different audiences. As such, we plan to improve the way in which Service 2 is advertised to highlight how it differs from Service 1.

Conclusion

In summary, we have organized three calls for Service 1 projects and one call for Service 2 projects in the first 18 months of ESiWACE. After some staffing shortages in the first year, the full set of granted Service 1 projects is currently up and running. As explained above, we have identified a few areas where we can improve, in particular related to communication and dissemination. While most service projects are still underway, we can already see that the performance of several applications is significantly improving, as is their capability to efficiently utilize modern HPC systems, including EuroHPC systems like Marenostrum 5 (BSC⁶) and Leonardo (CINECA⁷), and other national GPU clusters like Levante at DKRZ⁸ and Snellius at SURF⁹, thanks to the collaborations between RSEs and weather and climate modeling communities created by the ESiWACE3 Services.

⁶ <https://www.bsc.es/ca/marenostrum/marenostrum-5>

⁷ <https://leonardo-supercomputer.cineca.eu/>

⁸ <https://docs.dkrz.de/doc/levante/index.html>

⁹ <https://www.surf.nl/en/services/snellius-the-national-supercomputer>